

Original Article

EFFECT OF TASK HIERARCHY ANALYSIS MODEL OF INSTRUCTION ON THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF STUDENTS IN BIOLOGY IN URBAN AND RURAL AREAS

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Abstract

The study assessed the effect of task hierarchy analysis model of instruction (THAMI) on the academic performance in Biology among secondary school students in urban and rural areas in Osun State. One research question and two null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted pre-test, post-test control group quasi-experimental design. Population of the study consist of 379 senior secondary school two students offering Biology drawn from 12 selected public senior secondary schools from three Local Government Areas in the state using multistage sampling procedure. The sample was divided into two groups; experimental group and control group. Instrument used for the data collection was a Biology Performance Test (BPT) containing 30 objective questions from paste WAEC question papers. The reliability of the instruments was ensured using Kudar-Richardson Formula 20 Analysis and reliability coefficient of 0.83 was obtained. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research question and determine the closeness of students' scores, while t-test and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) were uses to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings of the study showed that there is no significant difference in the achievement means scores of students in the experimental and control groups before treatment and that task hierarchy analysis model of instruction (THAMI) is a viable instructional strategy for enhancing biology learning outcomes. The result also revealed that location has statistical significant effect in the achievement mean scores of the experimental and control groups. Based on the findings, concluded that is an effective method of teaching biology. It was therefore, recommended among others that THAMI should be used in the teaching of Biology in the secondary school for meaningful learning among students.

Key Words: Assessing, Effect, Task Hierarchy Analysis Model, Instruction, Biology

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INTRODUCTION

Science education plays a pivotal role in the advancement of a nation as it makes it possible for necessary skills, knowledge and attitude for scientific literacy and technological innovation to be acquired (Osborne, 2018). The teaching methods used in teaching science by teachers at the secondary school greatly determine the performance of students. Studies have shown that more innovative-based strategies have significant impact on the way and manner in which students learn science than the traditional method. The works of Afolabi, (2020) & Ogunniyi, (2020) revealed that students exposed to innovative and problem-solving methods always perform better than their counterparts in the traditional method. Innovative methods also facilitate and enhance understanding and retention of concept taught. Effective teaching and learning of science is crucial in equipping individuals with the technical knowhow to address the multiple challenges of our modern societies together with climate change, several health issues, pandemics as well as sustainable environmental resource management United Nations Education, Science and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO 2020). Similarly, Adeyemi, (2018) added that science education fosters national development through acquisition of scientific skills, knowledge and attitude for scientific literacy and innovation. The use of innovative method in teaching science will lead to students' curiosity, creativity, and acquisition of critical thinking skills among others. Bybee, (2017) posited that when students acquire these skills, it will empower them as citizens to take part in meaningful decision making processes that will positively reposition their countries Without effective teaching characterized by active participation, students would be left a resultant effect of acquisition of haphazard scientific

knowledge that will hinder the advancement of the country economically. Effective learning of science according to Adeyemi, (2018). is subject to quality of teaching, relevance of curriculum and availability of resources It is very crucial that present day Biology student to acquire relevant skills for success in the study of science at the tertiary education levels. This will bring out the best performances in demonstrating scientific competency and needed capabilities. The West African Examination Council Chief Examiner's report averred poor performance of students in biology is often is a reflection of the teaching methods adopted by their teachers. School location can also be a factor affecting secondary school students' performance in science subjects particularly, Biology. Public secondary schools in Nigeria are located in both urban and rural areas with unequal distribution of human and material resources. Studies have shown that science students in urban schools tend to perform better than their counterparts in the rural areas, (Adeyinka, 2020). Ogunkola, (2020) opined that in most cases is as a result of availability of better educational resources and more qualified teachers in the urban areas more than the rural areas. The extent to which school location determines students' performance is mostly based on the fact that teachers prefer urban schools where social amenities are likely more available to the detriment of the rural schools, and students (Ronfield, Kwol, & Reiningner, (2016). Also Adekunle, (2017) observed that students in the urban areas performed better in chemistry than their mates in the rural areas. Akinbote, (2022) reported that schools in rural areas are faced with other challenges such as limited access to well-equipped laboratories and under-equipped libraries with outdated textbooks among others. It should be noted also that areas with high levels of pollution

including noise can have adverse effect on the academic performance of students especially in science, as reported by Adeogun, (2022). It has been advocated that science teaching should be basically and essentially activity centered where by students learn by doing. Biology being one of the science subjects concerned with the study of living organisms should not be left out in these activity oriented. The Task Hierarchy Analysis Model of Instruction (THAMI) is a critical component of the instructional design process. It represents the steps in the instructional process which involves the breakdown of performance into detailed levels of specifications. According to Gagne and Briggs (1979), the most prominent task hierarchy analysis operates at the macro-level. It is used to identify and sequence the prerequisite skills or performances that lead to course goals. Macro- analysis usually implies unit or course level analysis. Task hierarchy according to Adeyemo, (2020) is a tool for enhancing student' understanding of complex concepts in biology. Furthermore, the works of Akinbote, (2020), (Okoro, 2017 & Ajewole 2019) all observed that task hierarchy analysis instruction makes cognitive load of the students simple. Studies on THAMI report improved students' engagement and motivation, enhanced understanding of complex concepts increased retention and transfer of learning, Task Hierarchy Analysis Model examines all relevant topics pre-requisite to the defined objectives or terminal task of a particular lesson. After a careful analysis of these pre-requisite topics and sub-topics, a hierarchical model is constructed in line with the identified pre-requisite topics to guide the teacher while teaching (Gagne & Briggs, 1979). To identify prerequisite that should be completed to facilitate learning at each level is of paramount importance. Pre-requisites according to Gagne are carefully identified by carrying out a simple exercise of task analysis in order sequence instruction properly based on learning hierarchy.

THAMI will tend to condense and de-bulk the entire Biology contents thereby making it easy for teachers to teach, easily retained by the student and retrieved from their cognitive structure. It was on this premise that the study on effect of THAMI on secondary school students' academic performance in Biology was conceived.

Statement of the Problem

The persistent failure of science students to obtain good grades in external examinations is a threat to the attainment of the goals of education generally and science education in particular. The use conventional method in the teaching of science only encourages mere memorization of the concepts taught and does not enhance deep understanding of scientific concepts, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills among students. Over dependence on the use of conventional method also does not allow students to take active part in learning which may result to lack of engagement and motivation as well as poor performance in science subjects, (Adeyemi, 2022). Students have continued to record poor performance in external examination in Biology because of teachers' over-dependence on the use of conventional teaching methods coupled with the influence of location where relevant resources are more available in schools located in urban areas while those in rural areas are neglected. Consequently, most students have failed to attain the level of mastery that would enable them to proceed to certificate courses in Biology and other science- related courses in general. The ugly situation has generated grave concern in the Nigerian education sector as well as among parents, sponsors and employers of labour. The problem of this study is that whether the use of task hierarchy analysis model of instruction (THAMI) will help to reduce or eliminate completely the difficulties students encounter in learning Biology and improve their performance is not clearly known. This makes imperative to conduct the study on effect of THAMI

on secondary school students' academic performance in Biology in urban and rural areas in Osun state to provide empirical data that will guide relevant stakeholders in taking remedial actions.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of task hierarchy analysis model of instruction (THAMI) on the performance of students in Biology in urban and rural areas in Osun state. Specifically, the study determined the effect:

- Task Hierarchy Analysis Model of Instruction on students' performance on the academic performance of secondary school students in Biology concepts.
- Location on THAMI on the academic performance of secondary school students in Biology concept

Research Questions

Unit concept of excretion.

Diagrammatic representation of the model of the study

Model of study represented as follows

Terminal Task or Desired Knowledge

Figure 1: Summary of Gagne's Task Analysis Model: Adapted from Gagne, 1965

Key:D – Terminal Task or Desired Knowledge
 A and B – Are necessary pre-requisites concepts for the terminal task or Desired Knowledge (D)
 a₁, a₂, b₁, b₂, etc. are the sub tasks or sub-ordinates for the terminal task

The listed products of metabolic processes such as urine, sweat, mineral salts, carbon iv oxide (a_{1,1} , a_{1,2} , a_{2,1} , a_{2,2} , b_{1,1} , b_{1,2} , b_{2,1}& b_{2,2}) respectively are other sub-tasks or subordinate tasks necessary for

One research question guided the study thus:

1. What is the effect of task hierarchy analysis model of instruction on students' performance in biology concept in Osun state?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the achievement mean scores of students exposed to Task Hierarchy Analysis Model and the control group before and after treatment.
2. There is no significant difference in the achievement mean score of students exposed to Task Hierarchy Analysis Model in the urban and those in the rural areas.

Scope of the study

The content scope of the study focused on the Biology

the terminal task or Desired Knowledge D.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed pre-test, post-test control group quasi-experimental design involving one experimental group and one control group. The sample for the study comprised 379 Senior Secondary School two (SSS11) Biology students selected from 12 public secondary schools from the three senatorial districts in Osun State using a multi-stage sampling procedure. Intact classes of senior secondary school two (SSS11) students offering

Biology were selected using purposive sampling technique. The instrument used for data collection for the study was (BPT) Biology Performance Test which contains 30 objective questions in which every correct answer scored one mark only while every wrong answer scored zero. The discrimination indices and difficulty index of the Biology Performance Test were adequately ensured through proper analysis by the experts and the discrimination ability was between 0.45 -1.0 and difficulty index of about 50% was obtained. The validity of BPT was determined by experts and suggestions of these specialists aided in the modification of the instrument's items, which were deemed legitimate and appropriate for the aim of the study. The reliability of the instrument was adequately determined. The researchers adopted a test-retest method carried out in two Senior Secondary Schools in Osun State that were not part of the study, Kuder-Richardson Formula 20 (KR-20). Reliability coefficient of 0.83 was obtained for BPT which shows that the instrument was reliable enough. The researcher designed a table of specification to determine before-hand how much weight to an attached to each unit and level of behavioural objective based on the unit content of excretion. The experiment was carried out in three

stages namely: pre-treatment stage, treatment stage and post-treatment stage. The use of task hierarchy analysis model of instruction was made up of four steps: The first step was the careful selection of a unit topic for the study; the second step involved the examination of all relevant topics and sub-topics that are prerequisite to the desired objective or terminal task. The third step involved careful analysis of these selected relevant topics and sub-topics. The last step was the construction of a hierarchical model in line with the identified prerequisite topics which is followed by the teacher while teaching. A total of six weeks was used to administer the treatment to the experimental group. The post-treatment stage witnessed the administration of properly reshuffled items of BPT in order to determine the effects of the teaching method on the students. The pre-treatment stage lasted for two weeks while the treatment stage lasted for six weeks, the data gathered were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics where applicable. Mean and standard deviation were utilized to answer the question and determine the closeness of the samples before and after treatment while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance

Table 1: Effects of Task Hierarchy Analysis Model of Instruction on Students' Performance in Biology concepts.

	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Difference
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Treatment Group	188	11.00	3.87	23.50	2.14	12.50
Control Group	191	11.39	3.20	14.77	2.48	3.38
Total	379	11.20	3.55	19.10	4.94	7.90

Table 1 shows that pre-test mean scores of the treatment group was 11.00 with standard deviation 3.87 while of the control group was 11.39 with standard deviation 3.20. The post-test mean

achievement score of 23.50 is higher than that of the control group which is 14.77. This shows a post-test mean achievement difference of 12/50 in favour of the control group. The result shows that Task

Hierarchy Analysis Model of Instruction enhanced students' performance in Biology concepts.

Testing of Hypotheses

Table 2: Summary of t-test of effect of THAMI on students' academic performance in Biology concepts before treatment

Group	N	Mean	SD	Df	t _{cal}	P
Treatment group	188	11.00	3.87			
Control group	191	11.39	3.20	377	1.062	0.289

p>0.05

Table 2 shows that there is no significant difference in the achievement mean scores of students exposed to Task Hierarchy Analysis Model and the Conventional group before treatment at 0.05 level of significance (t= 1.062, p>0.05). The null hypothesis

is not rejected since the P-value is greater than 0.05. It implies that the two groups were homogenous at the point of entry. Therefore, we refuse to reject the null hypothesis.

Table 3: Summary of t-test of students' academic performance in Biology concept after treatment

Group	N	Mean	SD	Df	t _{cal}	P
Task Hierarchy Analysis Model	188	23.50	2.14			
Conventional	191	14.77	2.48	377	36.722*	.000

***p<0.05**

Table 3 shows that there is significant difference in the achievement mean score of students taught Biology concept using Task Hierarchy Analysis Model of Instruction and those not exposed to the model after treatment (t_{cal}= 36.722, p<0.05) is

significant at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis was rejected and thus restated as: there is significant difference in the achievement mean scores of the two groups after treatment.

Table 4: Summary of t-test of students' academic performance in Task Hierarchy Analysis Model group by location

Location	N	Mean	SD	df	T	P
Rural	89	22.82	1.69			
Urban	99	24.11	2.32	186	4.324*	0.000

***p<0.05**

The result on Table 4 shows that the computed t-value (4.324) obtained for the groups with a p-value < 0.05 was statistically significant at 0.05 level, thus, null hypothesis is rejected

groups prior to treatment showing that the groups met at the same point of entrance and were homogenous. The study findings further revealed a substantial difference between the experimental and control groups' post-test mean achievement score with the performance of the treatment group improving significantly which was believed to have resulted from their exposure to treatment. This is in line with the finding of Adeyemo, (2020) who observed that the use of THAMI enhanced students' understanding of concepts taught. The study's findings revealed a substantial difference between

Discussion

The study's findings indicated that prior to treatment; there was no significant difference in the achievement mean scores of biology students in the experimental and control groups. Pre-test mean scores were low and comparable in the two groups. This demonstrated the homogeneity of the study

the experimental and control groups' post-test mean scores and standard deviation. There was a significant improvement in students' performance, which was believed to have occurred as a result of their exposure to treatment. The results indicated that individuals exposed to the Task Hierarchy Analysis Model of Instruction achieved higher mean achievement scores on post-test than those exposed to the Conventional technique. This is in line with the findings of Okoro, (2017) and Ajewole, (2019) who in their separate studies observed improved academic performance of the students exposed to THAMI. The findings of the study revealed a significant difference in the achievement means scores of the students exposed to task hierarchy analysis model of instruction in the urban and rural areas in favour of students in urban areas with Schools in the urban areas enjoying availability of better human and material resources with the students having access to some facilities that are not readily available in the rural areas according to Ronfield, Kwol, & Reiningner, (2016)... This finding supports the work of Adekunle, (2017) whose study revealed that students in schools located in urban areas had a better performance than their counterparts in the rural areas.

Conclusion

Findings of the study, which revealed that students exposed to Task Hierarchy Analysis Model of Instruction (THAMI) performed better than their counterparts taught with the conventional methods of teaching and that of students in urban areas performed better than those in the rural areas. Based on these findings, it was concluded that THAMI was an effective method for the teaching biology to improve performance of students in both urban and rural areas in Osun State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Biology teachers should improve their

instructional processes by making use of Task Hierarchy Analysis Model of Instruction for enhanced students' performance.

2. Science teachers should be trained through seminars and workshops on the use of THAMI for effective teaching of Biology.

3. It is also recommended that government and education stakeholders should make infrastructure, learning resources, available for schools irrespective of the location.

4. The school administrators and other stakeholders in education should provide a more conducive learning environment that will embrace the use of new methods of teaching Biology such as Task Hierarchy Analysis Model.

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